

SOS_AQUAE

Economic assessment

Analysis of irrigation and fertilization costs and incomes from the maize production comparing innovative digested microfiltration followed by drip lines fertigation technology (MFT+SDI) with the Business As Usual (raw digestate + urea + sprinkler irrigation).

	MFT+SDI	BAU	Delta
Irrigation €	835	495	340
S/L separation + microfiltration €	100	0	100
Digestate trasport and distribution €	120	120	0
Urea €	0	170	-170
Total Costs (€/ha)	1,055	785	270
Maiz yield (t/ha 33% d.m.)	68	60	8
€/ton of maize	45	45	0
Total Incomes (€/ha)	3,060	2,700	360
Profit (€/ha)	2,005	1,915	90

Microfiltered Digestate treatment to Fertigation: an environmental and economic sustainable solution

Objectives

To develop an innovative system to valorize the digestate liquid fraction (the most present and most problematic fraction to be valorised), for maximizing the efficient reuse of nutrients and reducing the use of mineral fertilizers through digestate microfiltration linked to microfiltered digestate injection into a fertigation plant with driplines in sub-irrigation.

Further details

- € **Total budget:** € 372.047,32
- € **Total financed:** € 330.042,59
- € **Main funding source:** Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups
- € **Rural Development Programme:** 2014IT06RDRP003 Italy - Rural Development Programme (Regional) - Emilia-Romagna

🕒 Ended, 2020 - 2023

📍 Emilia-Romagna, Italy

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Operational and investment costs of solid/liquid separation and microfiltration related to treated volume (with depreciation and equipment life 10 year)

Considering an electric power of 4 kW for pumping plus 7.5 kW for a digestate microfiltrate production of 6.2 m³/h, the total Solid/Liquid separation + MFT cost is less than 1.2 €/m³ if the volume treated is higher than 14500 m³ per year.

Main benefits

- Technically and economically feasible solution (low filtration cost)
- Digestate liquid fraction valorization
- Digestate fertilizer efficiency maximization
- Mineral fertilizers saving
- Ammonia emissions and nitrate leaching reduction
- Water and energy saving
- Reduction of soil compaction
- Chance of extending the agronomic period for the digestate spreading

Other applications

The system has been applied by the farm AB GROUP Societ Agricola S.R.L. for the fertirrigation of citrus and prickly pear in Sicily region <https://www.progettofertimed.it/servizi/>

Conclusions

The results obtained highlight that fertirrigation with microfiltered digestate in the drip lines is both technically feasible and economically and environmentally sustainable.

Fertirrigation with digestate in the drip lines, allow high productivity by reducing external inputs, and it is proposed as one of the most efficient and sustainable practices in the digestate management scenario.

The higher investment costs are balanced by savings in chemical fertilisers and improved yields, as well as more difficult to monetize environmental benefits.

Context

Slurry and digestates are very useful fertilizing materials for agricultural crops as they contain nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and numerous micronutrients.

Location in the Nutri-Know value chain

Microfiltered Digestate treatment to Fertigation, an integrated system to improve nutrient upcycling

Effective and affordable solutions for manure and digestate recycling, to increase the nutrient use efficiency and reduce the environmental impacts (ammonia and GHG emissions, nitrates leaching from soil to water), are becoming more and more necessary and widespread. This approach contributes to improve sustainability of the farming systems in the frame of circular economy.

The fertigation with digestate from biogas plants, a practice that significantly enhances nutrient use efficiency, is not yet widespread because of chemical-physical characteristics of digestate, even if clarified, that are such as to cause problems of clogging of the nozzles of the fertigation line.

The digestate, if properly filtered, can be used as a fertilizer resource mixed with irrigation water by two techniques: the first, in sub-fertigation with drip lines buried at a depth of 30 cm, the second in fertigation with rangers.

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